

A HISTORICAL STUDY OF THE NIGERIAN FILM INDUSTRY AND ITS CHALLENGES

Gloria ERNEST-SAMUEL

Department of Theatre Arts

Imo State University, Owerri

gloimsu@yahoo.com

ORCID:0000-0001-5066-8998

&

Divine Sheriff UCHENNA JOE

Department of Theatre Arts

Imo State University, Owerri

evgdivinejoe@yahoo.com

ORCID:0000-

Abstract

This paper examines the historical development of video films in Nigeria. It investigates underlining challenges that are peculiar to the growth of the industry. The research adopts the literary methodology as chapters in scholarly books, article in reputable journals and archival materials serve as reference point for the study. The paper reveals that numerous challenges abound in Nollywood productions. Numerous factors amongst culture has contributed to Nollywood's creative process and production. Also, the absence of social responsibility has also affected Nollywood's creative process. The study adopts literary methodological investigative approach as chapters in scholarly books and articles in reputable journals serve as our critical reference point. The study reveals that ethnic bias on the part of the filmmakers and piracy perpetuated by marketers have are some of the numerous challenges in the film industry. Although filmmaking is a sort of investment that requires recouping of finances invested, a balance should be created between the quest for economic gain and social impact in order to improve the quality of the films.

Key Words

Film – Nigeria – Nollywood – Challenges – Society - Responsibilities

Introduction

The rise of Nigerian video films to international recognition and acclaim has awakened the desire for a full-fledged scholarship on the industry. However, film studies being a recent trajectory in the Nigerian educational setting has attempted to come up with a concise, well researched documentation in relation to this but

such efforts have not put to rest the discourse on the subject matter. This paper, therefore intends to chart a comprehensive course in this regard by taking a divergent approach which is a critical evaluation of the impact of the industry's growth on cultural production over time and to highlight the inherent timeless challenges while proffering plausible suppositions with a view of bequeathing prospective film scholars a substantial reference material on the history and practice of video film in Nigeria. Obviously, historical in content and focus, it becomes imperative that a historical research approach fused with a dialectical perception will be adopted to further the course of this study.

Film in Nigeria

Film was introduced into Nigeria long before that official formation of the country but was within the colonial era. Williams Ahmed-Gamgum writes that, "on settling down in Nigeria, they created Northern and Southern Protectorates; they introduced and implemented Lord Lugard's "political memorandum", indirect rule: and amalgamated the Northern and Southern Nigeria in January 1, 1914" (117). Therefore, to bring this study into an academic focus for proper inquest, the paper categorizes this section that deals with the history of Nigerian video film practice into three Categories namely; The Colonial Era, Post-Colonial Era and the Nollywood Era.

The Colonial Era

The foundation of what we could call "the Nigerian film industry today was laid by the British colonialists. They introduced film to Nigerians as a form of entertainment, but they actually had the intention of using it to justify their imperialism and to transmit British's values and norms" (Azeez 5). However, the history of Film in Nigeria is closely related to vital periods in the history of Nigeria (Uchenna Onuzulike 177). Film was introduced into Nigeria in 1903, precisely eleven years before the official proclamation of the entity called Nigeria with a film show at the Captain Glover Hall in Lagos. The first film shot in Nigeria was in Jos, Plateau state in the then Northern Protectorate. The film was titled *Palaver* (Nigerian Film Corporation 1). In the same vein, Ohiri observes that film made its first entry into Nigeria through efforts of business merchants, the church and the colonial government and the 1903 exhibition was made possible by a Spanish firm, Balboa and Company who were invited by Herbert Macaulay (53). Herbert Macaulay's love for theatre-related practices and their embodiments as tools for nationalist activities during the struggle for independence in the colonial era was so much that one of Nigeria's foremost theatre practitioners, Hubert Ogunde had to write and premier a play on him to herald and immortalize Macaulay's contribution toward nationalist movement. Ebum Clark reports that,

The overt political plays which were either composed to expose the evil machinations of the colonial rule or to demand outright freedom are *Worse Than Crime, Strike and Hunger* (both 1945)... Although *Herbert Macaulay* appears political in character, Ogunde still insist, as he stated in his advertisement for this play in 1946, that it is basically a historical documentation on that famous politician's life (83).

This goes to substantiate the report that Herbert Macaulay actually brought Balboa and Company from Spain for the exhibition that year as he was a man interested in the arts. Studies on the films available during this period indicate that "the contents of these films were largely documentary and focused on topics of education, health, agriculture and industry amongst others. The Nigerian natives were shown films by means of travelling cinema vans because films were few and theatres did not exist in the remote areas" (Onuzulike, 178). At this period, businessmen traded on entertainment films while religious films were made by the missionaries. "The initial film distributors were mainly Lebanese and Syrians who brought in films from European distribution house with preference for those in London knowing that Nigeria was a British colony" (Okpadah and Afolabi, 19). With time, the films were exhibited in halls, fields and church premises as token fees were paid for entertainment films while most of the religious films were shown for free. The interest of Nigerians in films was minimally negligible until the Second World War broke out (Ohiri 53). It is recorded that when Balboa left Nigeria in September 1903, Stanley Jones, a European began showing films at the same venue. In 1907, the Catholic Priests in Lagos began showing films about the life of Jesus. By 1921, film began a popular means of entertainment in Lagos. "Later in 1929, a local experiment on the use of film of publicity for government health policies was carried out by a colonial official, W. Sellers in Nigeria" (Mgbejume). On happenings regarding cinema operation in colonial Lagos, Olubomelu reports that, Cinema houses were established in Lagos with the express permission of the colonial government from 1937. One of the earliest cinema operators in Lagos was the West African Pictures Company owned by Mr. S. Khalil, a member of the Syrian Community in Lagos. The company was granted the right to use Glover Hall Lagos, including its Tennis Court Gardens and bar for three nights a week for cinematographic shows. Later, the West African Pictures Company established Rex Cinema in Ebute Metta, Regal Cinema and Royal Cinema, Lagos in late 1930s and early 1940s. The other cinema house in Lagos during this period was the Capitol Cinema. Brian Larkin reports that:

Cinema in northern Nigeria occupies a distinct moral position which regulates who attends it. The first cinemas appeared in the

colonial period and were immediately associated with British colonialists and southern Christian Nigerians, leading to questions about their Islamic acceptability for Hausa Muslims...When cinema was first established in the city of Kano, it was located outside of the *Birni*, the traditional Muslim city of Kano, in the modern area of *Sabon Gari* (new town). The result was that in the minds of many Hausa, cinema became associated with the moral depravity that characterized the reputation of *Sabon Gari*. It became part of what was known as *barkiki* culture, associated with other illicit activities such as drinking alcohol, male and female prostitution, and pagan religious practices. This negative conception of cinema as a social space still continues today and the result is that cinema in northern Nigeria is an overwhelmingly lower class, male activity (2).

It was until 1947 that “an indigenous film unit called Federal Film Unit was established to replace the Colonial Film Unit (CFU). However, because it was still under the administration of the colonial government, it did little in terms of energizing local content” (National Open University of Nigeria, 19-20). It was under the administration of Richardson that this was done as Musa, Auwalu and Ndalnam Alhaji declare that, “Other pre-colonial constitutions that were made before Lyttleton, with the exception of Richard constitution of 1947 to some extent, all others were repugnant to a purposeful federal constitution” (318). The Cinematographic Law of Nigeria was enacted a year later in 1948 which touches on licensing of cinema premises, moral protection of the public and film censorship. This paved the way for the takeoff of film production in Nigeria unlike in the early years when most of the films exhibited were produced overseas. In the list of films produced during this period are *Empire Day Celebration in Nigeria* (1948), *Small Pox Leprosy* (1950), *Queen Elizabeth II's visit to Nigeria* (1956) which were all documentary films while feature films of this era include *Moral Disarmament* (1957). The colonial administration's activities regarding film in Nigeria culminated with the passage of the Entertainment Law in July, 1959 a year before the independence of Nigeria (Ohiri 54). October 1st, 1960 witnessed the independence of Nigeria with Lagos as its new capital.

Film in the Post-Colonial Era

On the state of film immediately after independence, Augustine-Ufua Enahora understands that, “the country inherited the colonial structure of film industry and, despite her political independence in 1960, the system has not changed. Nigeria is a cinematographic province of India and America while its colonial

masters are the Indians and Lebanese” (100). The first few years of the newly independent country was generally seen as formative and from study nothing really significant happened in terms of cinema or film development as the country galloped through various forms of crisis. The 1964 general election was however the biggest crisis of all as it was alleged to be neither free nor fair. This was followed by chains of reactions starting with the first military coup on 15th January, 1966, and a counter coup on 29th July, 1966 which swept Ironsi from power and installed Yakubu Gowon. Nwaobi reports that on 30th May 1967, Ojukwu declared the secession of the eastern region of Nigeria and consequently declared the establishment of the independent Republic of Biafra which resulted in a war between 6th July, 1967 and 12th January, 1970 (5-6). Cinema could be said to have been in limbo throughout these turbulent periods.

Immediately after the war, Cinema activities experienced resurgence and began to receive attention of both government and individuals. In 1972, the first law on government protection for Nigerian cinema was enacted. Known as Nigerian Enterprises Promotion Decree No. 4 of 23rd February, 1972, also popularly known as the Indigenization Decree, the law stipulates that cinemas and other places of entertainment were reserved for Nigerians and a certain percentage of the income from gates should be remitted to the government. The law enabled and energized indigenous film practitioners, and resulted in the first film shot by a Nigerian production company, the Calpenny Nigeria limited here in Nigeria. “The film was titled, *Kongi’s Harvest*. Other films like *Child Bride*, *Bull Frog in the Sun*, *Son of Africa*, *Golden Women*, *Home Message* followed suit till 1975 when the first feature film recorded in Nigerian language (Igbo language) *Amadi* which was produced by Afro-Cult Foundation limited” (Ohiri 54-55). It was in recognition of the potentials of film as a tool for national development that the Federal Government in 1979, established the Nigerian Film Corporation. However, in 1982 following “the Enabling Act, the Nigerian Film Corporation was established by the President Shehu Shagari administration. Under the Shagari administration, the National Film Distribution Company (NFDC) was also established and equipped to take over the film distribution from American Motion Picture Export Company (AMPEC)” (Ohiri, 56). The Shehu Shagari administration was an entertainment friendly government considering the great leap taken by the industry during that era.

The account of the development of film in the postcolonial time cannot be complete without a mention of the role of the broadcast media industry in Nigeria. The mid-1980s witnessed the establishment of local broadcasting stations in virtually all the regions which generated local content from indigenous popular theatre groups in cities like Lagos to make up their shortage in local

programmes production which was as a result of the law that limited foreign television content. These theatre groups later moved from just recording their performances for television to small scale informal video business with distribution across parts of the country. Between mid-1970s and early 1980s, government sponsored many of these informal film practitioners on technical courses outside the shores of Nigeria. Later on, coerced by the World Bank, the Nigerian government was forced to privatize many sectors, including media with less investment in television. This left a large chunk of professional television film makers jobless. However, in their quest to survive their ordeal, they encountered the new digital technology. This encounter established the pathway for the next era (Asogwa et al. 100).

The Nollywood Era

Ojukwu and Ezenandu note that, “the term, ‘Nollywood’ coined following the style of Hollywood (referring to the American film industry) and Bollywood (referring to the Indian film industry) is the generic name for the Nigerian film industry” (21-22). Onuzulike is of the opinion that:

The Nollywood emerged as a result of several factors, one being economics. The cost of video technology, coupled with greater awareness and demand for home entertainment, led to the rise of video film producers. In addition, the military government and the introduction of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) further affected the economy, resulting in reduced funding for celluloid productions (178).

The Nollywood era could be described as a child of circumstance. This era did not start out initially as Nollywood but just a film industry operating in the trajectory of a new technology. Alessandro Jedlowski writes that, “the name ‘Nollywood’ appeared in Nigeria for the first time in a *New York Times* article by Norimitsu Onishi in September 2002 and was republished by the Nigerian newspaper, *The Guardian* few days later” (228) indicating that the name for which this era is referred to, came exactly ten years after its take off. Even though Adesina Azeez notes that Ola Balogun sees the concept of Nollywood as a derogation of the Nigerian film industry, which reflects a low-cost approach to film-making that is accustomed to cutting corners and economizing on quality and content (16-17), yet the name subsists. According to Oyewole Sandra and Olajide Oyewole, “The direct-to-videos (VHS, VCD and DVD) distribution system which is a hallmark of Nollywood was triggered in 1992 with the film, *Living in Bondage*, the first commercially successful movie shot straight-to-video. It heralded a new era of Nigerian filmmaking...” (2).

Corroborating this, Alawode and Fatonji state that, “Nollywood was given impetus in 1992 when businessman Kenneth Nnebue wanted to sell a large shipment of videocassettes from Taiwan and decided they would sell faster if they had something on them. The production of *Living in Bondage* thus gave birth to what became the second largest industry in Nigeria after agriculture...” (62).

Furthermore, Barnard and Toumi point out that, “other filmmakers soon followed Nnebue’s footsteps and over the past 15 years, Nollywood has grown to become the third most prolific film industry after Hollywood and Bollywood in terms of number of titles released annually. Today, Nollywood is experiencing transnationality, international collaboration and acceptance as Alessandro Jedlowski reveals that:

Three films in particular can be seen as the avant-garde of the new wave: Jeta Amata’s *The Amazing Grace* (2006), Kunle Afolayan’s *Irapada* (2007), and Stephanie Okereke’s *Through the Glass* (2007). These films represent three different levels at which processes of transnationalization are transforming the video industry: modes of production, audiences, and settings (37).

Currently, there is now an evident resurgence of cinema culture which most producers have engaged in the premiere of videos films and as well recoup their money before letting out this films to distributors. On this, Jedlowski adds that:

Stephanie Okereke’s *Through the Glass* reflects another tendency within the framework produced by transnationalization processes...When released in Nigeria, this film earned more than 10 million naira (almost US\$65,000) at the box office in three weeks, solely through theatrical release in a handful of Nigerian cinemas. It was the first theatrical success of its kind, and it clearly showed many industry practitioners that the revival of cinema-going culture was a phenomenon to be taken seriously (38).

This era cannot be discussed conclusively without a mention of the development of Nigerian Christian filmmakers under the Umbrella body known as Association of Nigerian Christian Evangelical Dramatist (ANCEDRAM) with pioneer Mount Zion Faith Ministries founded by Mike Bamiloye leading the line. Others include The Breakthrough Ministries, Kay Technical Evangelical, Evangelical Outreach Ministries (EVOM), The Reconciliation Ministries, POGEM Television Ministries, etc (Ogunleye 109-110). Within the last decade of Nollywood, a number of sub film industries have emerged and are thriving to fulfill the needs

of their immediate audience. These sub-film industries include “Kannywood located in Kano in Northern Nigeria, Urhobowood of the Urhobo people in Delta state Nigeria, Yoruwood in Western Nigeria” (Okpadah 322), and Igala films in Lokoja.

Today, Nollywood has grown to become both an entertainment and economic institution. Next only to crude oil, it is positioned as Nigeria’s greatest export and economic pillar (Musa x). Despite these giant strides made by Nollywood, Ernest-Samuel and Uduma note that, “it is often common to hear African film scholars address Nollywood as an informal industry” (47). On the surface, informality could connote many things but Ramon Lobato puts the aforementioned observation in proper perspective. He notes that:

Informality has been central to the success of the industry, with pirates building up a vast regional audience for Nigerian films. However, as producers attempt to formalise, regulate and consolidate the industry, informality is being recast as a threat to long term sustainability. This tension between formality and informality, latent in many of the shadow film economies we have looked at thus far, is a defining feature of the Nigerian video industry as it enters its third decade (56).

Buttressing further on the informality of the industry, Lobato specifies that “Nollywood is clearly unlike other film industries. There are no formal distribution companies, just individual marketers and pirates, and in the place of cinemas there are video clubs and street markets. This is why Nigeria has been overlooked as one of the giants of global film culture” (59). This tends to be an incurable reoccurring decimal in the existence of the industry. Tracing this problem historically, Ernest-Samuel and Uduma observe that Nollywood emerged through the efforts of traders in the electronic business, with little or no government intervention which results in the prevalence of informality in the operations of practitioners in the film industry. This implies that from the beginning, film distribution in Nollywood was equally localized and dependent on illiterate or semi-illiterate marketers domiciled at the Ebinpejo lane at Idumota market, Lagos, and Iweka market, Onitsha, respectively. Their level of literacy invariably shaped the method of film distribution or marketing. These marketers who also double as executive producers coupled with the non-existent distribution structures puts extra pressure on filmmakers. Although the industry has grown to become a million-naira business, the environment remained unappealing as a result of the inability of the distributors to look beyond the financial aspect of filmmaking. This scenario leaves the industry at the mercy of

individuals with little or no idea of filmmaking calling the shots from pre-production to post-production as long as they have the financial capacity to take on the venture. In addition, the industry is visibly unregulated as the government which did make any significant input at the developmental stages of the industry still finds it very difficult to fashion a workable way of exercising/enforcing a level of control cum regulation on the industry. By so doing, the informality in the industry is so enshrined to the point that it has become its main stay. "Thus, one can argue that informal film production and distribution will keep thriving owing to the politics of interest geared towards personal enrichment on the part of the key participants in Nigerian film industry" (44-66). Lamenting the effect of the informality of the industry on productions most especially the cultural aspect, Azeez states that,

Nobody can argue with the fact that the production values of the films are awful; their narratives are excessively melodramatic, and they are often so dramatically simple that audiences can predict the end of the films; they are hastily produced in a way that exposes the cheap and vulgar conditions of the production. Probably it is because of the melodramatic tendencies and dramatic excesses in their narratives that Nigerian films appear vulgar to Western viewers, Nigerian academics and early professional filmmakers. Thus, the impression of Nollywood outside Nigeria is nothing more than that of curiosity; and to the local professionals, it is nothing more than an expression of charlatanism. However, it must also be pointed out that the films are produced on tiny budgets. Indeed, Nigerian audiences are also critical of the poor technical and aesthetic qualities of the films, but they appreciate the social cultural roles the films play in their lives... the films offer what Turner calls *liminoid* (18).

"The filmmakers cash in on Nollywood fans' appreciation of cultural or epic productions to produce cheap, poor quality films enriched with impressive folksongs and music. Such productions provide them with options of producing video films and musicals at almost the same cost, and selling them to the audience as different productions" (Ernest-Samuel and Uduma 58). Thus, making such productions irrelevant beyond mere entertainment. Oshiotse Okilagwe notes that by so doing, "The Nigerian film producers do not seem to have developed adequate capacity especially the perspective skills needed to develop and produce such films that could bring about reorientation of our national value system" (56).

Nollywood Video Film, Social Responsibility and Challenges

Over the years there have been questions about the negligence of social responsibility films by many filmmakers which has become an obvious challenge to the industry in terms of quality. While examining this issue, Popoola observes that, “a worrisome aspect of all the films is that none of them actively canvass for the discouragement of the negative tendencies acted out on the screen. Many of the film producers merely see their art as a means of livelihood, and do not view themselves as possessing a responsibility to the society” (135). Even though I disagree that this is obtainable in all films as stated by Popoola, this attitude towards production has deepened the anti-societal norm in the industry which film scholars have outlined as one of the banes of Nollywood developing into a formidable tool for social transformation. This is closely linked to ethical breaches that are evident in the industry. Ethics are by and large not externally imposed but developed from within the society or group that subscribes to it. These ethics are usually handed down by previous generations and the ethics of an industry like Nollywood cannot radically differ from that of the larger society as arts which filmmaking in part reflects the society. So, the art should both mirror and heal the society of its perceived ills.

Among alleged ethical breaches in Nigeria video films are sexual immorality, including nudity, deification of wealth and opulence, witchcraft and voodoo, tendentious handling of facts, romanticisation of official corruption and perverted moral values and other socially invalid trends (Ogu Enemaku 71-72).

Another major challenge being faced by the industry is the distribution and marketing irregularities. According to Haynes and Okome:

The main problem on the market is piracy, “Piracy is our AIDS,” ... Popular videos are rapidly pirated, sometimes by the marketer entrusted with distributing the film... The producers have a number of grievances against the marketers. They are accused of being merely traders, not true distributors, as they are largely uninterested in advertising the films or otherwise building the market... Because in many cases they put up the capital for video productions, they are in a position to determine casting and as a cartel they can kill films in which they have no cultural or financial interest (30-31).

The actions of the marketers pose a great deal of danger and result in other challenges to the industry as there is a chain effect of their uninspiring role. The investors lose their money and are afraid to attempt further; their determination of cast lead to stereotypical casting as only casts in their cabal are frequently used which may likely result to poor output, half hazard interpretation of roles and less

opportunity for young and exuberant artistes thereby limiting the number jobs created by the industry. Furthermore, funding of Nollywood is still challenged by lack of operational structures in the industry. Spending and sales are quite informal as most filmmaking houses cannot say actual number of films sold or funds spent in the making process. The outlets are not properly structured in such a way that it can remit directly back to the production houses. Also, the viewing culture of most Nigerians is not helping the attempt to use cinemas to checkmate this irregularity.

Closely linked to the aforementioned is imbalance in artistic output or creativity and financial gain. Mistry, Jyoti and Ellapen submit that:

The content, its mode of production and distribution of Nollywood films reflects an entrepreneurial, grassroots mode. The implication for this model of film making is that it shifts the emphasis away from the important considerations- first, the idea of social transformation and second, the value of film as creative expression- and instead privileges the economic (capital) over and above all other concomitants (66).

In addition, the technical knowledge applied in the productions are obsolete when compared to those used in advanced countries. This is because latest technological apparatus of filmmaking are not easily available and accessible to filmmakers in Nigeria as a result of economic setbacks. The unavailability of a streamlined and monitored national film policy has also not aided the representation of Nigeria in Nollywood films unlike in Hollywood where there are guiding policies that are enunciated in order to promote the image of America. There is little room or a total lack of it in most cases for criticism in Nollywood. This is because, most unenlightened filmmakers see critics as ‘destroyers’ or ‘spoilers’ and so do everything possible to side track them in the process while in actual sense, there should be a pre-premiere preview of films by critics whose opinion will be use to correct anomalies of a production before it is let out for public view. This action rather than improve the output quality suppresses it to the lowest standard.

No sector will experience rapid growth with high rate of nepotism and endemic favoritism in Nollywood. Individuals colonize the facets of the industry and force their own people on productions for personal aggrandizement or other unethical reasons. This robs the industry of rich reserve of manpower and options culminating stagnation and consistent insipid productions as most professional are denied opportunities because of lack of spread out accommodation by these individuals. Finally, inaccessibility to facilities such as airports, military base and

apparatus, and other places regarded as sacrosanct in Nigeria have hampered the ability of filmmakers to come up with 'out of the box' filmic ideas. Where accessible, they are so exorbitant that it most times discourages many filmmakers who lack the required financial power to undertake such ventures.

Conclusion

This paper explored the historical development of video films in Nigeria. It investigates underlining challenges that are peculiar to the growth of the industry. The study reveals that ethnic bias on the part of the filmmakers and piracy perpetuated by marketers are some of the numerous challenges in the film industry. In the light of the findings, the research recommends that filmmakers should endeavour to engage film scholars to subject their films to criticism before they are premiered and sold. Although filmmaking is a sort of investment that requires recouping, a balance should be created between quest for economic gain and social impact in order to improve the acceptability of the films. Also, government should take more seriously, the issue of instituting stringent measures as quality control systems and also provide adequate support through subventions for the Nigerian film industry to facilitate the production of films with quality that would compete internationally. Soft should be provided to filmmakers. In the same vein, universities undertaking courses in film production and film studies should be encouraged and duly funded by the government.

Works Cited

- Ahmed-Gamgum, Williams A. "Nigeria at 100 Years: The Process and Challenges of Nation Building." *Public Policy and Administration Research*, vol. 4, no. 8, 2014, pp. 114-129.
- Alawole, S.O. and Fatonji, S.I. "Ritualism in Nigerian Home Videos." *1st Annual International Interdisciplinary Conference AIIC*, 2013, pp. 62-72.
- Asogwa, C.E., Onoja, I.B. and Ojih, E.U. "The Representation of Indigenous Culture in Nollywood." *Journal of Scientific Research & Reports*, vol. 7, no. 2, 2015, pp. 97-107.
- Azeez, Adesina L. "From Informality to "History and Evolution of Nollywood: A Look at Early and Late Influences" *Nollywood in Global Perspective*. Ed. Bala A. Musa. Palgrave Macmillan, 2019, pp. 3-24.
- Bala, Musa A. "Nollywood and the Globalization of Prosocial Entertainment" *Nollywood in Global Perspective*. Ed. Bala A. Musa. Palgrave Macmillan, 2019, pp. 127-146.
- Barnard, Helena, and Krista Tuomi. "How Demand Sophistication (De-) Limits Economic Upgrading: Comparing the Film Industries of South Africa and

- Nigeria (Nollywood)". *Industry and Innovation*, vol.10, no. 1080, 2008, n.pp.
- Clark, Ebun. *Hubert Ogunde: The Making of Nigerian Theatre*. University Press PLC, 1979.
- Enemaku, Ogu S. "Ethical Foundations of Nigerian Video Film: Towards a Re-Construction." *African Video film Today*. Ed. Funke Ogunleye. Academic Publishers, 2003, pp. 69-80.
- Ernest-Samuel, Gloria and Uduma, Ngozi. "From Informality to "New Nollywood". Implications for the Audience." *Nollywood in Global Perspective*. Ed. Bala A. Musa, Palgrave Macmillan, 2019, pp. 44-66.
- Haynes, Jonathan and Onookome, Okome. "Evolving Popular Media: Nigerian Video Films." *Nigerian Video Films*. Ed. Jonathan Haynes. Kraft Books LTD, 1997, pp. 21-43.
- Jedlowski, Allesandro. "From Nollywood to Nollywood: Processes of Transnationalization in the Nigerian Video Film Industry." *Global Nollywood The Transnational Dimensions of an African Video Film Industry*. Ed. Matthais Krings and Onookome Okome. Indiana UP, 2013, pp. 25-45.
- "When the Nigerian Video Film Industry became "Nollywood": Naming, Branding and the Videos' transnational mobility." *Estudos Afro-Asidicos* vol. 33, no. 1/2/3, 2011, pp. 225-252.
- Larkin, Brian. "Hausa Dramas and the Rise of Video Culture in Nigeria." *Nigerian Video Films*. Ed. Jonathan Haynes. Kraft Books Ltd, 1997, pp. 105-125.
- Lobato, Ramon. *Shadow Economies of Cinema*. Mapping Informal Film Distribution. Palgrave Macmillan, 2012.
- Mgbejume, O. *Dramatic TV, Film Scripting*. Redeemer House Publishers, 1989.
- Mistry, Jyoti and Jordache A. Ellapen. "Nollywood Transportability: The Politics and Economics of Video Films as Cultural Products. *Global Nollywood The Transnational Dimensions of an African Video Film Industry*. Ed. Matthais Krings and Onookome Okome. Indiana UP, 2013, pp. 46-72.
- Musa, Auwalu and Ndaliman A. Hassan. "An Evaluation of the Origins, Structure and Features of Nigerian Federalism." *Valley International Journals* vol.1, no. 5, 2014, pp. 314-325.
- Nigerian Film Corporation. *Nigerian Film Corporation*.
- National Open University of Nigeria. *Documentary Film Production*. N.p. n.d.

- Nwabueze, Emeka. *Research Methods. An Integrated Approach*. 2nd ed., ABIC Books, 2013.
- Nwaobi, Godwin C. "The Nigerian Wars, Regional Crisis and Ethnic Disturbances: Policy Responses and Democratic Implications." *Qualitative Economic Research Bureau* (n.d): n.p.
- Ogunleye, Foluke. "Christian Video Film in Nigeria: Dramatic Sermons through the Silver Screen." *African Video Film Today*. Ed. Foluke Ogunleye., Academic Publishers, 2003, pp. 105-128.
- Ohiri, I. C. *Introduction to Media Arts*. Lilino Ventures Publishers, 2002.
- Ojukwu, C.C. and Ezenandu, P. E. "A Paradigm shift from Tradition to Modernity in Nollywood's Projection of African Narratives." *Global Journal of Human Social Science* vol. 12, no. 5, 2012, pp. 21-26.
- Okilagwe, Oshiotse A. "Exploring Cultural Engineering and the Film in Nigeria." *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Scholarship. Special Issue- Motion Picture in Nigeria*, no. 3-5, 2008, pp. 54-63.
- Olubomehin, Oladipo O. "Cinema Business in Lagos, Nigeria since 1903." *Historical Research Letter* 3, 2012, pp 1-10.
- Onuoha, Chikezie. *Bioethics Across Borders*. Uppsala Universitet, 2007.
- Onuzulike, Uchenna. "Nollywood: Nigerian Video films as a Cultural and Technological Hybridity." *Intercultural Communication Studies* XVIII, no. 1, 2009, pp. 175-187.
- Oyewole Sandra and Olajide Oyewole. "A Peek inside Nigeria's Film Industry." *Wipo Magazine*, April 2014, pp. 2-5.
- Okpadah, Stephen and Afolabi, Taiwo. The video film medium: A panacea for national development. *Journal of English literature and cultural studies*. Vol. 2 (3): 17-27. <https://jelcsjournal.com/article-1-94-en.html>. 2019
- Okpadah, Stephen. Urhobowood Home Videos and the Poetics of cultural documentation. In: Martins Tugbokorowei and Chukwuma Anyanwu (eds.) *New aesthetic dimensions in African drama and theatre: A festschrift in honour of Prof Sam Ukala* (320-331). Delta State: Association of Nigerian Authors. 2018.
- Popoola, I. S. "Nigeria and the Challenges of Violent Video Films." *African Video Film Today*. Ed. Foluke Ogunleye. Academic Publishers, 2003, pp. 129-140